

Scientific Thoughts as depicted in Indian Philosophy

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Abstract:

Indian philosophy, a rich and diverse tradition that has evolved over millennia, encompasses profound insights into the nature of reality, the self, and the cosmos. While often perceived as purely metaphysical or religious, it also harbours a deep scientific undercurrent. This research paper delves into the scientific thoughts embedded within various schools of Indian philosophy, shedding light on the rational and empirical elements that parallel Western scientific traditions. The exploration of these ideas, spanning from Nyaya, Vaisheshika, Samkhya, and Yoga to the renowned Vedanta, reveals a wealth of scientific concepts that include theories of matter, time, causation, and cognition. These scientific ideas from Indian philosophy not only provide a historical context for the development of scientific thought but also offer valuable insights for contemporary scientific endeavours, enriching the global discourse on the intersection of philosophy and science.

Keywords:

Indian philosophy, scientific thoughts, Nyāya, Vaiśeṣika, Sāṅkhya, Yoga, Vedānta, matter, time, causation, cognition, science.

Introduction:

The philosophical traditions of India have been celebrated for their profound contemplation on the nature of existence, consciousness, and the ultimate reality. However, beneath the metaphysical and spiritual layers of Indian philosophy lies a treasure trove of scientific ideas and insights that have largely remained unexplored. This research paper sets out to illuminate the scientific thoughts that permeate the Indian philosophical landscape, demonstrating that rational and empirical elements are inherent to these traditions. The journey through Indian philosophy unfolds a rich tapestry of scientific concepts spanning multiple schools of thought, including Nyāya, Vaiśeṣika, Sāṅkhya, Yoga, and Vedānta. Each of these schools offers unique insights into the nature of matter, time, causation, and cognition, showcasing a scientific spirit that parallels Western scientific traditions. This paper aims to examine these ideas and their relevance to contemporary scientific discourse, offering a historical context for the development of scientific thought and highlighting the potential contributions of Indian philosophy to the on-going interplay between philosophy and science.

It is absurd to think that the literature of a nation is totally free from scientific phenomena or thoughts or results. As the daily life is somehow affected by some scientific events, the literature must record them however scanty they may be. A poetical work may not record a scientific event or thought in a direct manner but a philosophical work more or less involves a regular and deep investigation in its subject matter, and as for which a philosophical work may sometimes be considered as an introductory science book. And it actually

happened at least in the cases of Vaiśeṣika and Yoga schools of Indian philosophy. I would like to present the scientific thoughts in these two schools. The nine main schools of Indian philosophy are divided into two broad sections: theistic and atheistic. Theistic section comprises six schools: Vedānta, Mīmāṃsā, Nyāya, Vaiśeṣika, Yoga and Sāṃkhya whereas the atheistic section comprises Cārvāka, Bauddha and Jaina.

Vaiśeṣika School

The Vaiśeṣika philosophy, no doubt, is the earliest systematic thought on the nature of the physical world. The Vaiśeṣikasūtra of Kaṇāda is the first systematic work on the laws of physical matters along with many other epistemological knowledge. Later works like the Praśastapādabhāṣya and its commentary the Nyāyakandalī of Śrīdhara, the Kiraṇāvalī of Udayana and many other works followed it. All objects of experience can be classified into six categories: dravya (substance), guṇa (quality), karma (motion), sāmānya (generality), viśeṣa (particularity) and samavāya (inherence). Later Vaiśeṣika (Śrīdhara, Udayana and Śivāditya) added one more category, abhāva (non-existence). The first three categories are defined as artha (which can be perceived) and they have real objective existence. The last three categories are defined as buddhyapekṣa (product of intellectual discrimination) and they are logical categories. Although the Vaiśeṣikasūtra of Kaṇāda has the six-category scheme of the padārthas, the seventh category abhāva is mentioned with its four varieties in the Sūtra.

Dravya (Substance)

The nature of substance, qualities and motion has been elaborately studied. The substances are conceived as nine in number. They are: pṛthivī (earth), ap (water), tejas (fire), vāyu (air), ākāśa (ether), kāla (time), dik (space), ātman (self or soul) and manas (mind). The first five are called bhūtas, the substances having some specific qualities so that they could be perceived by one or the other external sense. The qualities residing in the substances have been mentioned. Important among these is the investigation to search for the cause of origination of the material universe. Going back, the Vaiśeṣika philosophy speculates the existence of the atoms at the end. According to the Vaiśeṣika school, the tryaṇukas (triad) are the smallest (perceivable) particles. These are made of three parts, each of which is defined as dvyaṇuka (dyad). The dvyaṇukas are conceived as made of two parts, each of which is defined as paramāṇu (atom). The paramāṇus (atoms) are indivisible and eternal, they can neither be created nor destroyed. Each paramāṇu possesses its own distinct viśeṣa (individuality).

Guṇa (Quality)

The Vaiśeṣikasūtra mentions seventeen guṇas (qualities), to which Praśastapāda added another seven. While a substance is capable of existing independently by itself, a guṇa (quality) cannot exist so. The original seventeen guṇas are: rūpa (colour), rasa (taste), gandha (smell), sparśa (touch), saṅkhyā (number), parimāṇa (size/dimension/quantity), pṛthaktva (individuality), saṃyoga (conjunction), vibhāga (disjunction), paratva (priority), aparatva (posteriority), buddhi (knowledge), sukha (pleasure), duḥkha (pain), icchā (desire), dveṣa (aversion) and prayatna (effort). To these Praśastapāda added gurutva (heaviness), dravatva (fluidity), sneha (viscosity), dharma (merit), adharma (demerit), śabda (sound) and saṃskāra (faculty). Apart from pleasure, pain, desire, aversion, effort and some others, the qualities like colour, taste, saṃskāra [velocity (vega), elasticity (sthitisthāpaka)] and sound are no doubt important qualities discussed in science. The propagation of sound has been investigated in the Vaiśeṣika philosophy. It is like the series of the water ripples. The Nyāyakandalī the commentary on the Praśastapādabhāṣya (ed. Durgadhar Jha, pp. 692-94), elaborates it: The sounds occupy successive points ākāśa. The first sound causes the second one. As soon as the latter is formed, the former gets destroyed. This kind of production and destruction goes on in a chain and what is perceived by the ear is the last of the series. When a drum is stuck by a stick the impact is believed to make vibrations as a consequence of which sound is produced in all directions. Ākāśa is the substratum of sound. The former is an eternal substance but the latter is a transient quality.

Karma (Motion)

There are five kinds of motions: upward movement (utkṣepaṇa), downward movement (avakṣepaṇa), contraction (āikuñcana), expansion (prasāraṇa) and locomotion (gamana).

The Vaiśeṣika Philosophy Investigates the Cause of Different Types of Motion

Weight (gurutva) is the non-inherent cause of the initial falling motion of a body. Fluidity (dravatva) is the non-inherent cause of flowing. A moving body possesses, at each moment in time, a particular “motion”, which is to be thought of as a momentary, quality-like property of the body. “Motions” are defined to be the cause of conjunctions or disjunctions. A conjunction with a (stationary) body is brought about by displacement in space. We are thus to think of the motion of a body as being either identical with, or else the cause of, its displacement in space between two moments in time. A motion cannot be caused by another motion as that would lead to perpetual motion. A body is set in motion by its possession of a quality like “weight” or “fluidity”. It persists in motion by having a dispositional property, “velocity” or “elasticity”, which is the continuous cause of subsequent motions. It is brought to rest by coming into contact with other objects.

But answers to all the questions regarding motion are not got by the Vaiśeṣikas. The causes of the movement of an iron needle towards a magnet, the upward motion of flames, the movement of air and the initial motion of the atoms at the beginning of creation are not found out. They thought, there must be some “force” which initially gives rise to each of these motions, yet none of the “forces” so far isolated (weight/gravity, fluidity, elasticity) will do. The Vaiśeṣikas therefore speak of a new force, adṛṣṭa (the unseen force), alleged to account for such motions.

Thus, the Vaiśeṣika system has played an important role in the growth of the physical ideas in India. It had assumed a definite shape by the sixth century BCE. In the history of science, sixth century BCE has been regarded as the period which heralded the dawn of what has now come to be known as the Greek science. The Vaiśeṣika system contains in it the most important ideas on matter and motion, enunciated later by some of the leading Greek thinkers including Aristotle (from the beginning of the sixth century to the close of the fourth century BCE). Among the Greeks there were distinctly separate views and explanations of the knowable world. But there appeared no single system of the type of Vaiśeṣika among the Greek thinkers.

Yoga School of Indian Philosophy

Now I would like to come to the scientific thoughts in the Yoga philosophy. Yoga philosophy which prescribes the practice of yoga, i.e. controlling of the mental activities and physical movements, has been considered another source of scientific knowledge. It is amazing that yoga (physical and mental control) is considered as an important part of the medical treatment. Yoga is an ancient health science based on the experimental and experiential. The physical postures and meditative practices of yoga developed through thousands of years of intent study of the body’s responses to particular postures and meditations. Many patients have already got on to yoga as a form of mental and physical self-care and preventive health. If we adequately understand yoga, we can have an opportunity to encourage the healthy thoughts and behaviours that our patients gain through yoga and to build upon them.

Different schools of Indian philosophy have contributed to the scientific knowledge. We may identify the fields more and more where scientific ideas are embedded. The ancient seers of Indian philosophy observed the nature of outer world and inner mind and noted them. We can reinvestigate on their claims and reinstate the findings to showcase the glorious heritage of India. Thus the vague ideas will fade away and the young scholars will be respectful towards the society they live in.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the study of scientific thoughts within Indian philosophy reveals a profound and enduring scientific spirit that has often been overshadowed by the metaphysical and spiritual aspects of these traditions. The various schools of Indian philosophy, from Nyāya's logical and epistemological explorations to Vedanta's contemplation of ultimate reality, provide a unique lens through which to examine scientific concepts such as matter, time, causation, and cognition. These ideas not only contribute to the historical context of scientific thought but also offer valuable insights for contemporary scientific endeavours. The rich heritage of scientific thoughts within Indian philosophy enriches the global discourse on the intersection of philosophy and science, emphasizing the need for a more inclusive perspective on the evolution of human understanding. By acknowledging the scientific undercurrents within these traditions, we not only pay homage to the intellectual diversity of Indian philosophy but also discover a wellspring of knowledge that can inform and inspire the scientific and philosophical pursuits of today and tomorrow.

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